

ISic0075

I.Sicily inscription 0075

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

aedicula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Timpone di S.Antonio

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644810

Bibliography

Académie des inscriptions et belles-lettres, 1881-1962. Corpus inscriptionum
Semiticarum. Paris. At 1.138

Amadasi Guzzo, M.G. 1967. Le iscrizioni fenicie e puniche delle colonie in
Occidente. Rome. At Sic.Pun.05

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 363-364
Slouschz, Nahoum 1942. Thesaurus of Phoenician inscriptions.
At 117
Donner, Herbert, Röllig, Wolfgang 1962-1964. Kanaanäische und aramäische
Inschriften. Wiesbaden. At 63
Lidzbarski, M. 1907. Kanaanäische Inschriften: (moabitisch, althebräisch,
phönizisch, punisch). At no.57
Garbini, G 1967. Catalogo delle iscrizioni fenicie conservate nel Museo
Archeologico Nazionale di Palermo. *Kokalos*. 13: 66-72. At 66 no.1
Whitaker, Joseph I. S. 1921. Motya, a Phoenician colony in Sicily. London. At 274
n.1

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